

**ASSESSMENT OF THE BALANCED HOUSING DEVELOPMENT COMPLIANCE IN
THE PHILIPPINES: THE CASE OF CEBU CITY**

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Abstract

As an urban development strategy, the goal of balanced housing development is part of the framework plan that will provide socialized housing for the underprivileged and homeless. It is in line with the government objective of tapping the support of the private sector in housing the poor. Balanced housing development require developers of proposed subdivision to develop an area for socialized housing equivalent to at least 20% of the total subdivision area or total subdivision project cost and other modalities as compliance.

This study examines the compliance of balanced housing development program in Cebu City, its contribution in housing the poor and in urban development. In particular, the paper sought to know what modalities were availed in the compliance, how it fares to the housing backlog of the city, and what its role in urban development. It focuses on the 52 compliance projects of real estate developers in Cebu City for the period of 2003 to 2014. The study found out that there are 1,525 house and lot units, 871 lots or a total area of 81,723.4 square meters provided as proof of compliance; the common mode of compliance is through development of a socialized housing equivalent to either 20% of the total project area or 20% of the total cost of the main project. The balanced housing compliance in Cebu City is a dismal contribution in providing affordable housing to the poor. The developer's choice of mode of compliance was premised not only to comply, but to profit. Balanced housing development was implemented in the narrow context of providing "shelter", not in urban development. In longer perspective, balanced housing development should inspire us towards the path of a sustainable and balanced community.

Keywords: *balanced housing; socialized housing; housing policy; sustainable development*

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ASSESSMENT OF THE BALANCED HOUSING DEVELOPMENT COMPLIANCE IN THE PHILIPPINES: THE CASE OF CEBU CITY

Cebu City is the capital city of the Cebu province and is the "second city" of the Philippines, being the second most populous metropolitan area in the country after Metro Manila. Cebu is a significant center of commerce, trade and education in the Visayas and Mindanao. It is the Philippines' main domestic shipping port and is home to about 80% of the country's domestic shipping companies. Cebu City has a land area of 315 square kilometers. But in spite of this "urbanization", it is not free from homeless and informal settlers. Out of the total 195,461 households, 46.5 percent owned or amortized the lots that they occupied. Moreover, 20.0 percent of the households occupied lots which were rent-free but with consent of the owner, 24.1 percent rented the lots that they occupied while 6.2 percent occupied lots which were rent-free but without consent of the owner. (NSO) The housing backlog continues to grow. The estimated unmet housing needs which are popularly called "housing backlog". The Philippine housing backlog currently stands at 5.5 M and Cebu City has 41,000 families living in informal settlements in public and private lands.

Meanwhile, the balanced housing development program was formulated as part of the over-all strategy to uplift the conditions of the underprivileged and homeless citizens in urban areas and in resettlement areas by making available decent housing at affordable cost. The Republic Act 7279, or the Urban Development and Housing Act of 1992 (UDHA), mandates all subdivision developers to build socialized housing equivalent to either 20% of the total project area or 20% of the total cost of the main project and other modes of compliance.

The Housing and Urban Development Coordination Committee (HUDCC) set the maximum price of a socialized housing at P450, 000.00 per unit. It can be a row house with a floor area of 18 square meters and with 36 square meters lot area. The said amount should be availed by those Pag-ibig members after payment of reservation fee, transfer fee and other processing fee. The law provides that a beneficiary needs to register with the City Government to avail of the program. Based on the data of the Division for the Welfare of Urban Poor, there are 58,712 total registered beneficiaries and 40,327 beneficiaries benefited from the city in coordination with other government agencies (DWUP, 2010).

This study examines the compliance of balanced housing development program in Cebu City, its contribution in housing the poor and in urban development. In particular, the paper sought to know what modalities were availed in the compliance, how it fares to the housing backlog of the city, and what its role in urban development.

I. Theoretical Framework

At present, there are scholarly journals and studies of the implementation of balanced housing development program that deals on the assessment of the technical and administrative capacities of local officials to implement the socialized housing provision of the UDHA (Buendia, 1998) and the modalities to ensure of its implementation, particularly in Davao City (Pampanga et al 2015).

In his study, Ramos posited that the strategy oftentimes did not produce integrated communities where low and high income households are both physically and socially interwoven.

Also, balanced housing has so far not shown visible results in terms of spatially integrating affordable housing with other kinds of land uses in the city (Redoblado, 2013).

The study previously conducted in Davao City concluded that the NHA and the LGUs are the responsible for the implementation and monitoring compliance with the balanced housing policy. The devolution of functions to the local governments does not include the monitoring of the balanced housing policy compliance.

Furthermore, a study conducted by Buendia concludes that the gross discrepancies and inconsistencies between Local Government Unit (LGU) and HLURB records on evaluation and monitoring proved that these two government agencies have weak collaborative and coordinative system as well as communication linkage (Buendia, 1998). Ballesteros adds that the compliance to the balanced housing provision of the UDHA has not been adequately monitored especially at the local level (Ballesteros, 2009).

II. Methodology

The study will apply a quantitative and qualitative approach in the analysis. It will mainly rely on primary data generated from the HLURB and the City Government. Interviews will be conducted with HLURB, City officials and real estate developers. Site visits will be conducted randomly in the compliance project.

III. Data, compliance and processes

In 1992, Republic Act 7279 (UDHA) was enacted into law. One of the main features is the implementation of balanced housing development program, with the government objective of tapping the support of the private sector in housing the poor. In lieu, incentives were given for developing socialized housing such as exemption from the payment of project-related income taxes, capital gains tax on raw lands used for the project, VAT for the project contractor, transfer tax for both raw and completed projects, and donor's tax for lands that have been donated for socialized housing purposes.

Balanced housing development program require developers of proposed subdivision to comply with the 20% of socialized housing through different modalities. UDHA classifies the mode of compliance as the following: (1) Development of an area for socialized housing equivalent to at least twenty percent (20%:) of the total subdivision area or total subdivision project cost. The socialized housing shall be developed within the same city or municipality, whenever feasible; otherwise, it shall be allowed elsewhere in the Philippines. (2) Development of new settlement through Joint venture project of the developer with it subsidiary or with other HLURB-accredited developers for the 'production of new socialized housing; (3) Contribution of the developer in new socialized housing projects of HLURB-accredited non—government organizations; (4) The provision of educational facilities, 'ihealth facilities, productivity/livelihood centers, and other Amenities and facilities; (5) Slum upgrading or renewal of areas for priority development either through zonal improvement programs or slum improvement and resettlement programs of NHA;(6) Joint-venture projects with either the local government units or any of the housing agencies; (7) Participation in the community mortgage

program; The real estate developers will submit the 20% compliance project to the HLURB. Once it will be approved, the latter will issue a certificate of compliance and will approve the license to sell of the main project.

In 2012, the City Government of Cebu thru its legislative counsel formulates an Implementing Rules of Regulation to Ordinance 1770 (An Ordinance Implementing Balanced Housing as provided for in Section 18 of RA 7279, otherwise known as the Urban Development and Housing Act of 1992, and providing for the Mechanism Thereof) that prescribe rules, policies and procedure in implementing RA 7279. It outlines different modes of 20% balance housing compliance in Cebu City, including “deposit an amount for socialized housing program”, as an additional mode of compliance. This ordinance makes Cebu City as the only local government unit that has localized the balanced housing provision of UDHA.

a. Mode of compliance

Data obtained from HLURB shows that there are 58 projects in the period of 2000 -2014 that complied with the program. It is equivalent to 2,090,905.90 square meters total land area developed. The said projects resulted in the delivery of 1,525 house and lot units, 871 lots or total area of 81,723.4 square meters. Interesting to note that out of 58 projects, 43 were categorized as open market, while only 9 projects were Economic project class. Open market category is high-end to open market residential projects, while the economic projects are those housing that fall in medium to low cost level. Most of the projects were located in Talamban, Pardo, Banawa and others. (Figure 1)

Meanwhile in the compliance projects, development of new settlement is the dominant modality for the compliance of balanced housing in Cebu City. Compare to other modalities, this is a developer-controlled mode of compliance. Under this modality, the developer acquires and develops lots, construct housing and offer to the market. For the developers there are advantages with this mode of compliance. It is less tedious since developers will do the site selection and arrange with the concerned local government and national agencies, and importantly, they can market the project to the public. Definitely developers have the expertise and resources on these aspects (Table 3).

The joint venture scheme covers primarily local government units of Cebu City and other municipalities. The LGU contributes the land and was the lead implementer with overall responsibility in the selection of beneficiaries and in the operation and management of the resettlement sites. On the other hand, the developer contributes funds for the development of site and housing construction and provides technical expertise for the preparation of project plans until completion (Table 4).

This was also the case in in collaboration with Gawad Kalinga, the developer contributes funds for the projects of the latter equivalent to the 20% compliance. The agreement signed by the both parties will suffice as compliance to the 20% balanced housing program. The other mode of compliance was less significant, for it was not availed by the developers.

. Furthermore, the study also reveals that the 36 real estate developers with main projects in Cebu City complied with the 20% balance housing program implemented by the city government

through deposit an amount for socialized housing program of the city, for the period of October 2012 to April 2015.

b. Key Players

The compliance framework has sets of actors that monitor the implementation of the program – National government agencies, local government, developers and non-profit organizations. The HLURB was mandated as the sole regulatory body which grants licenses to private developers to sell their products in the market. Before a private developer be granted license to sell (LTS) and Certificate of Registration, they should comply with the 20% balanced housing socialized program. License to sell is a license to owner and developer in selling lot, house and lot or condominium in the market, while Certificate of Registration will enable the developer to register and protect the public from fraudulent transactions. The City Government of Cebu on the other hand, which is in-charge in issuing Locational Clearance (LC) and Development Permit (DP), requires the developer to present proof of compliance on the balanced housing development before the City Council approves. The LC certifies that the project is located in its proper zone under the city land use plan, while DP ensures that land development plans are satisfactorily complies with the National Building Code and other laws on subdivision development (Figure 1).

IV. Analysis

On the 20% compliance, the 1,525 house and lot units provided through the program is a mere 5.8 % of the 41,000 families living in informal settlers or 11 % of total housing backlog of 21,000 households in Cebu City. In the whole, the 58 compliance projects is a mere 3.9% (81,723.4 square meters) out of the total area of the main projects (2,090,905.90 square meters).

By **mode of compliance**, most of the developer constructed projects on their own compare to the other modalities. Palawan et al argues that this joint ventures and partnership with other developer runs counter to the concept of balanced housing. It seems logical since in different commercial centers and business establishments, different social groups works together, while they live in different places. The presidents, executive officers are living in Maria Luisa, Beverly Hills and Pristina, their clerk, salesladies, workers, and drivers are living in Minglanilla, Consolacion, Compostela or in the informal settlers area. In addition, providing the program on their own have been a business for developers. It cost less to produce a unit of housing if they constructed the housing, about 17% or P 25, 000 per unit, on the average, in compare to incremental housing (Ballesteros, 2013). And there are other “add-on” in the price of socialized housing such as processing fee, addition improvement, reservation fee and confirmation fee.

By **location**, there are more outside Cebu City compliance projects than with-in the city projects developed for the period; Cebu City has 19 compliance projects only. The new settlement sites located in Cebu Province totaled 21 projects, while outside Cebu is 7 projects. A comparison of

cost per unit shows that on the average, off-city projects cost less per unit than in-city projects by about P13, 000 per unit (Ballesteros, 2013). The cost difference arises mainly from the land cost.

On the contrary, among the different modalities, joint venture with the developers is more advantageous to the city in ensuring compliance of projects within its jurisdiction. The city government should maximize its owned land and buildings and forge ties with the developers. Based on the report of Land Management Council (LMC), the City Government owns at least 20 properties in the city. These properties could be used as contribution in a joint venture with the developer in developing socialized housing. Second, the city registered beneficiaries of the program have more chances of being prioritized.

The coordinative mechanisms of key players for the housing and urban development services are generally weak. Having a shelter is one of the barometers of urbanization, but the program in Cebu City helps in marginalizing the informal settlers to distant places. Both of them monitors the program in the context of providing shelter, not in holistic approach of providing transportation, infrastructure, facilities and urban development. Besides, the framework for urban development is epitomized in the comprehensive land use plan of the city, which will allocate land for socialized housing, but unfortunately the city government failed to promulgate since 1996. The HLURB should assist the City Government in formulating a CLUP and it will also strengthen their coordination and cooperation in implementing programs for the poor.

V. Conclusion and Recommendations:

The current implementation of socialized housing, provided by the private sector as compliance to the program, is a meager contribution in minimizing the housing backlog in Cebu City. It also marginalizes the socialized housing programs to far-flung and remote areas. In light of current fiscal constraints, it has to be seen as a complement private effort in providing affordable housing and their contribution in reducing housing backlog in the city and country as a whole. Balanced housing program should be viewed not only in the perspective of “shelter”. It is not tied up with any policy that has to do with provision of community facilities, amenities and economic opportunities that cater to both the 20% and 80% of the households (Ramos, 2013). Housing strategies can be tailored to local conditions, but it should be based with current realities. The continuing growth of housing backlog in Cebu City did not only stem from within the city, but includes migration and poverty in rural areas. It is therefore important for the government to provide jobs and livelihood to the rural areas.

Balanced housing development is a step towards creation of a balanced community. In its annual gathering of planners and developers, Urban Land Institute highlighted the importance of diversity as the hallmark of a healthy and balanced community. A healthy community provides a variety of housing types appropriate for residents in all stages of the life cycle; safe and affordable housing for people in all income groups; and housing opportunities close to jobs. The state and local regulatory policies offer cost-effective opportunities to make private housing more available and affordable. (Urban Institute, 2013).

Policy recommendation:

1. Reaffirm the balanced housing program. The government should stop in allowing developers to implement compliance projects in far flung areas. Instead, provide more incentives for the developers to encourage compliance within the city.
2. Strengthen the coordination among key players in monitoring the compliance. Strengthen the capacity of the local government in providing socialized housing and foster greater coordination with HLURB, NHA, NGOs and other agencies in monitoring of the compliance to the balanced housing development.
3. Formulation of Comprehensive Land Use Plan. The city government should pursue in formulating comprehensive land use plan and identify suitable land for socialized housing. They should be at the forefront in forging collaboration and cooperation with the developer in providing socialized housing to its people.
4. Pursue urban and rural development. The government should provide more income and employment opportunity to the people and rationalized government development programs both in rural and urban. As Mangawang pointed out, in order to address urban development and housing for low income groups, mechanisms for land assembly and allocation must be coordinated among the line agencies and LGUs, especially those in the urban fringe areas, where land is cheaper and access is ensured.

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Table 1. LIST OF PROJECTS WITH SOCIALIZED HOUSING COMPLIANCE IN CEBU CITY (2000 – 2014)				
Main Project	Socialized Housing Compliance/Locations	No. of Units		Area
		H&L	Lot	
Pinecrest Residences	MOA with Duraville Realty Devt. Corp. Cavite City	103		
Lessandra Talamban Pulangbato, Cebu City	Lumina Plaridel, Culiowa, Bulacan	104		
Dreamhomes Guadalupe Subdivision, Guadalupe, Cebu City	MOA with Gawad Kalinga, Cebu City		6	
Camella Talamban Pit-os, Talamban Cebu City	Sagay City Govt. Workers Village, Sagay Negros Occidental	7		
Kasyan Homes Highway 77, Talamban Cebu City	Sugbo GK Village, Gawad Kalinga Minglanilla Cebu	8		

Josefa Country Homes Guadalupe, Cebu City	Sugbo GK Village, Gawad Kalinga Minglanilla Cebu	53		
Brentville Homes Lahug Cebu City	Within the subdivision	31		
La Gracietta Homes	JVA with Talisay City			
Desana Heights Subdivision Quiot, Cebu City	Greenwoods Executive Village III		23	5,250
Lissandra Miramonte Talamban, Cebu City	Northville 14 Resettlement, Mabalacat Pampanga	85		42,598
Monterazzas de Cebu Ph 1-B North Ridge Guadalupe, Cebu City	City of Cebu			20,700
Woodberry Drive Subdivision Labangon, Cebu City	La Montana Subdivision	13		564
Villa Alessanda Talamban Cebu City	Palo, Leyte	18		738
Pristina North Ph 2 Bacayan, Cebu City	Compostela, Beachline Community			8,565
Casa del Rio Subdivision	La Montana	20		752
The Highlands of Maria Luisa, Busay, Cebu city	Dancing Sun Phase II			13,282
Pristina North Ph 2	Compostela, Beachline Community	8		8,565

Bacayan, Cebu City				
Redstone Village Subdivision, Pulangbato, Cebu City	Dancing Sun Subdivision			2,986
Leyson Ville Subd, Talamban, Cebu City	Within the project		92	3,292
Greenwoods Phase II-C Subdivision Pulangbato, Cebu City	Greenwoods Executive Village III- SH			1,686
BF City Homes Punta Princesa, Cebu City	La Montana Subd Cabangahan, Consolacion, Cebu	24		1,110
Monterrazas de Cebu Ph I Subd Sapangdaku, Guadalupe, Cebu City	Moa with City of Cebu SP-07-3122 dated 6/27/07		462	148,118.3
Metropolis I-D Subdivision Pulangbato, Cebu City	(MOA) JVA w/ LGU-Cebu City			210
Prsitina North (Lot 1788,10291 & 10295) Bacayan, Cebu City	Compostela Beachline Community Estaca, Compostela, Cebu	191		6,123
The ROD Village Subd. Sapangadaku, Cebu City	Gawad Kalinga-Budlaan Budlaan, Cebu City		27	1,000
Virginia Hills Subd Talamban, Cebu City	Windfields I-A Subd. Tolo-Tolo, Consolacion, Cebu			

Metropolis i-C Subdivision Pulangbato, Cebu City	Greenwoods Ph III Pulangbato, Cebu City			2,520
River Valley Community Subd. Kalunasan, Cebu City	Gawad Kalinga Community Fdn			3,541
Casa Rosita Subdivision Tisa, Cebu City	Asianville, Subd-Yati, Liloan Greenville Subd-Yati, Liloan	33 52		
San Marcelo Homes Subd. Kalunasan, Cebu City	Within the project	75		3,120
Alta Vista Phase II-A Subdivision Bulacao, Cebu City	Vista Grande SH-2 Candulawan, Talissay City			3,066
Alta Vista Phase I-A Bulacao, Cebu City	Vista Grande SH-1 Bulacao, Talisay City			2,315
Greenwoods Phase III-A Pulangbato, Cebu City	Within the project			1,895
Pristina North II-A Subdivision Bacayan, Cebu City	Compostela Beachline Estaca, Compostela, Cebu	157		7,176
Pristina North I-D Subdivision Bacayan, Cebu City	Compostela Beachline Estaca, Compostela, Cebu	11		500
Acacia Place Subdivision Banawa, Cebu City	Joanna Legacy Homes-Yati Yati, Liloan, Cebu	11		1,476
West City Homes Subdivision	MOA-NHA/ Dumaguete			1,684

Banawa, Cebu City	Resettlement Project			
Hacienda Salinas Subdivision Salinas, Lahug, Cebu City	Lopezville Subdvision Bayawan, Negros Or.	133		7,196
Pristina North P I-C Subdivision Bacayan, Cebu City	Balamban Community Housing, Poblacion, Balamban, Cebu	133		2,752
Maryville Subdivision Ph. IV Pilos, Cebu City	Casili Hills-SH Casili, Consolacion, Cebu			1330
Greenwoods Executive Village Pulangbato, Cebu City	Greenwoods Executive Village Iii Pulangbato, Cebu City		55	13,958
Bacayan South Ph. I-A &B Subdivision Bacayan, Cebu City, Cebu	Mandayao Hills Subd Pandol, Balamban, Cebu			13,992.4
Greenwoods Executive Village I-B Palungbato, Cebu City, Cebu	VL-Townhomes II-D Bacayan, Cebu City	16		3,373
Alta Vista II-B Subdivision Bulacao, Cebu City, Cebu	Vista Grande-SH 2 Candulawan, Talisay City			1,879
Greenwoods Executive Village III Pulangbato, Cebu City, Cebu	Greenwords Executive Village III-SH Pit-os, Cebu City			2,810
Metropolis Subdivision Pit-os &Pulangbato, Cebu City	Greenwoods Executive Village III- SH		205	20,806

	Pit-os, Cebu City			
Villa Del Rio II Subdivision Pit-os, Cebu City	Villa Leyson Townhomes II-B			8,034
Deca Homes—Bacayan Subdivision Bacayan, Cebu City	Within the project			3,099
Villa Leyson Townhomes-F Subdivision Bacayan, Cebu City	Within the project			791
South Hills Extension Subdivision Tisa, Cebu City				4,359
Maryville Subdivision Ph. III Talamban, Cebu City	Casili Hills-SH Casili, Consolacion, Cebu	15		6,064

Table 2. Number of Households by Tenure Status of the Lot: Cebu City 2010	
Tenure Status of the Lot	Number of Households
Total	195,461
Owned/being amortize/owner-like	90,951
Rented	47,054
Rent-free with consent of owner	39,076
Rent-free without consent of the owner	12,197
Not reported	127
Not applicable	6,056
Source: National Statistics Office, 2010 Census of Population and Housing	

New Settlements	39
Joint Venture with LGU	5
Joint Venture with Private Developer	2
NHA SUP	1
Gawad Kalinga and Habitat	5

Projects	Developer
Monterrazas de Cebu	Genvi-Agro Industrial
Metropolis I	Sta.Lucia Realty Development Corp.
Virginia Hills Subdivision	Felix Gochan & Son Realty

Table 5. Projects Compliance (within the main project)	
Main Project	No.of units/Area
Brentville Homes Lahug	31 hl
Leysonville Subdivision Talamban, Cebu City	92 Lots/3392 sq.m.
Odevillas Subdivision Tisa, Cebu City	14 hl/1,000 sq.m.
San Marcelo Homes Subdivision Kalunasan, Cebu City	75hl/3120
Greenwoods Ph III A Pulangbato, Cebu City	3,066 sq.m.
Greenwoods Ph III A Pulangbato, Cebu City	2,810 sq.m.
Deca Homes Bacayan Subdivision	3,099
Villa Leyson Townhomes –F Bacayan, Cebu City	791
Nichols Park Subdivision Guadalupe, Cebu City	83hl/7,884 sqm

Figure 1. Mode of Compliance in Cebu City

Figure 2. Location map of the main and compliance projects

Figure 3. Dancing Sun Townhomes Pricelist

DANCING SUN TOWNHOMES, PHASE 2
AVAILABLE PRIORITY UNITS PRICELIST, As of MARCH 2010

BLK.	LOT	LOT AREA (in sq.m.)	UNIT TYPE	CONTRACT PRICE	ADDL LOT PRICE & IMPROVEMENT	ESTIMATED LOANABLE AMOUNT	BALANCE	PROCESSING FEE	PROCESSING DISCOUNT PROMO *	DISCOUNTED PROCESSING FEE	TOTAL REQUIRED CASH-OUT	RESERVATION FEE	CONFIRMATION FEE (Payable w/n 30days)	REQUIRED CASH-OUT BALANCE	
19	1	64	End	400,000.00	25,000.00	425,000.00	400,000.00	25,000.00	72,250.00	49,750.00	22,500.00	47,500.00	10,000.00	20,000.00	17,500.00
	2	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	3	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	4	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	5	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	6	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	7	64	End	400,000.00	25,000.00	425,000.00	400,000.00	25,000.00	72,250.00	49,750.00	22,500.00	47,500.00	10,000.00	20,000.00	17,500.00
	8	64	End	400,000.00	25,000.00	425,000.00	400,000.00	25,000.00	72,250.00	49,750.00	22,500.00	47,500.00	10,000.00	20,000.00	17,500.00
SOLD	9	64	(Juni)	400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	10	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	11	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	12	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	13	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	14	64	End	400,000.00	25,000.00	425,000.00	400,000.00	25,000.00	72,250.00	49,750.00	22,500.00	47,500.00	10,000.00	20,000.00	17,500.00
	15	71	End	400,000.00	68,000.00	468,000.00	400,000.00	68,000.00	72,250.00	49,750.00	22,500.00	90,500.00	10,000.00	30,000.00	50,500.00
	16	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	17	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	18	71	End	400,000.00	68,000.00	468,000.00	400,000.00	68,000.00	72,250.00	49,750.00	22,500.00	90,500.00	10,000.00	30,000.00	50,500.00
20	1	64	End	400,000.00	25,000.00	425,000.00	400,000.00	25,000.00	72,250.00	49,750.00	22,500.00	47,500.00	10,000.00	20,000.00	17,500.00
	2	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	3	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	4	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	5	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	6	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	7	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
	8	91	End	400,000.00	106,000.00	506,000.00	400,000.00	106,000.00	72,250.00	49,750.00	22,500.00	128,500.00	10,000.00	30,000.00	88,500.00
SOLD	9	64	End (Mar)	400,000.00	25,000.00	425,000.00	400,000.00	25,000.00	72,250.00	49,750.00	22,500.00	47,500.00	10,000.00	20,000.00	17,500.00
22	4	64	End	400,000.00	25,000.00	425,000.00	400,000.00	25,000.00	72,250.00	49,750.00	22,500.00	47,500.00	10,000.00	20,000.00	17,500.00
	6	64		400,000.00		400,000.00	400,000.00	-	70,750.00	50,000.00	20,750.00	20,750.00	5,000.00	5,750.00	10,000.00
23	22	89	End	400,000.00	100,000.00	500,000.00	400,000.00	100,000.00	72,250.00	49,750.00	22,500.00	122,500.00	10,000.00	30,000.00	82,500.00
	30	89	End	400,000.00	100,000.00	500,000.00	400,000.00	100,000.00	72,250.00	49,750.00	22,500.00	122,500.00	10,000.00	30,000.00	82,500.00
31	TOTAL REMAINING PRIORITY UNITS														

LEGEND:

- * LIMITED PROMO ONLY!!!
- ** PAYMENT OPTIONS MORE THAN 2 MONTHS IS SUBJECT TO APPROVAL
- *** 1-Yr payment option is not recommended under the promo offer.

NOTES:

1. Prices and terms are subject to change without prior notice and approval.
2. Contract price is exclusive of electric & water meter installation fees which are to the account of the buyer.
3. Take-out charges/deductions should be paid to the developer upon take-out prior to move-in (this includes 1mont adv. Amort, MRI)
4. Reservation fee is non-refundable and non-transferable.
5. Confirmation fee & monthly cash-out balance payments should be issued w/ post-dated checks (PDCs) w/n 15 days from date of re
6. 24 months Pag-IBIG monthly amortizations should be issued with PDCs upon advice of the developer.
7. All payments should be made payable to MRDC.
8. Special discount promo applies to priority units only!!!

Source: Maria Luisa Properties

Figure 4. Dancing Sun Townhomes, Bolinawan, Carcar City

Photo taken at the site by AB Agosto

Figure 4-b Dancing Sun Subdivision 2 level House

Photo taken at the site by AB Agosto

Figure 5 . Dancing Sun Townhomes, Bolinawan, Carcar City

Photo taken at the site by AB Agosto

Figure 5-b Dancing Sun Townhomes, Bolinawan, Carcar City

Photo taken at the site by AB Agosto

Figure 6 Villa Leyson Talamban Cebu City

Photo taken at the site by AB Agosto

Figure 6-b Villa Leyson Talamban Cebu City

Photo taken at the site by AB Agosto